

THE ROLE OF PARENTS AND TEACHERS IN THE DISCLOSURE OF A CHILD'S ABILITY

Kayumova Gozal Narzullayevna

Teacher of the Department of Psychology, TerDu

E-mail: gkayumova234@gmail.com

Suyunova Dildora Halimovna

TerDu is a student of Applied Psychology

E-mail: dsuyunova586@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565042>

ANNOTATION

In this article, it is explained that adults should notice, support and motivate the child in time when the abilities that are clearly visible in children of junior school age and kindergarten age.

Key words: Parent, child, ability, attention, environment, education, motivation, teacher, development, consequence of neglect, skill.

Enter. Children are the happiness, future and pride of the family. The responsibility of parents to their children is huge. Cooperation between parents and teachers is very important for the child to become a mature person in the future, in learning and education. The child is the future of the country. It is necessary to create an opportunity to show his interests and abilities.

Nowadays, attention to education and youth has increased to a high level. Many opportunities are being created for young people to become perfect people in the future, to acquire a profession. The reforms being carried out in this regard are also bearing fruit. In order for the child to find his own way in the future, to develop into a knowledgeable person serving the country, it is necessary to pay attention and support to him from a young age. When a child is just entering kindergarten or school, sparks of ability and talent may begin to appear. Ability is an individual psychological characteristic. Ability depends on processes such as acquiring knowledge, skills, and qualifications. Ability is being able to take advantage of opportunities. Our abilities are mainly manifested in activities. In children with special abilities, their dynamism is manifested in the fact that they are interested in many things and constantly ask questions. Sparks of talent can also begin to appear when playing with toys with friends, how to use them, what shapes to use, and when he is interested in examining something carefully. Children of primary school age are more interested in learning. Some of them can show themselves through activities such as painting through imagination, and some of them can show their originality in playing musical instruments, reading poetry, dancing. At such a time, the teacher-pedagogue

should be able to correctly assess their abilities, give them the right direction, and support them. Of course, in this place, the responsibility, role and attention of the parents towards the child's future will be extremely great. Parents should create conditions for the child's interest and unique abilities. For example, it is considered necessary to bring a musical instrument or colored pencils, to act together with the child and help him spiritually. If adults notice and try to develop the ability that has started to shine like a flickering oil in a child, the child will grow spiritually and self-confidence will increase. But neglect can cause the child to sink mentally, lose interest, and even disappear later. Knowledgeable and capable parents give birth to perfect children who make a worthy contribution to the welfare of the country. A positive relationship with a child causes his interests and abilities to emerge. It is necessary to work with the child and answer his questions. If a child is interested in an activity, he wants to do it. But after trying it, later, as a result of his interest in another field, his interest in it may decrease. Forcing a child to be interested in something based on his own wishes may not lead to a positive result. The child should know that his opinions are taken into account and should have self-confidence. A capable, talented child will not achieve much if he does not use his opportunities. Ability appears in skill. Ability develops through interaction with the environment and education. Foreign psychologists Termen, Spearman, Kettel and others were engaged in the quantitative description of abilities and their measurement. They used mental aptitude tests as a way to measure ability. This method serves to collect information about abilities, not the intellectual aspect. In this place, L. S. Vygotsky mentioned his view. "Abilities do not exist outside of human activity. The composition of abilities is reflected in the speed of the child's achievements in the educational process. "It is important for the pedagogue to know what the student's abilities are and, consequently, what individual psychological characteristics of the student's personality are capable of performing activities, that is, how quickly and easily the student acquires skills and knowledge compared to others is important.

Summary. Thus, a child is a sprout that has just sprouted. Adults are responsible for its correct and beautiful growth. A child should be satisfied with his abilities, his talent, which can be an example to others. In this he needs motivation. The teacher should try to form motivations related to the educational content and educational process in the child. The child tries to demonstrate intellectual activity while completing tasks, to observe through thinking, to use his knowledge against difficulties in completing tasks in the educational process.

The attention, love, and spiritual encouragement of adults will be a great service for the child to contribute to the development of our country in the future.

References:

1. F. I. Khaidarov, N. I. Khalilova General psychology/textbook/Tashkent, INNOVATION-INTELLIGENCE"-2019. Pages 332-343.
2. Ismoilovna, A. Z., & Narzullayevna, K. G. (2022). In the Process of Forming a Person, Overcoming the Emotional State in The Family Environment. Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 6, 31-33.
3. Narzullaevna, G. K. (2022). Psychological analysis of factors that destroy family strength. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(6), 1528-1523.
4. Usmonovna, N. A. (2022). Raising children is the biggest responsibility. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(6), 1524-1529.

